

PLASTICIZING AND WETTABILITY ENHANCING COATINGS ON CARBON,

SILICON-CARBIDE AND BORON FIBERS

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This paper is concerned with two groups of coatings on high-modulus and high-strength fibers for reinforcing composite materials with metal and polymer matrices. The first group includes coatings improving and stabilizing the strength of fibers through a plasticizing effect. In the case of carbon fibers, the best results have been obtained by chemically applying a nickel coating 1 micron thick with subsequent annealing at 1,000°C to form a solid solution of carbon in nickel. In the case of boron and silicon-carbide fibers, the effect of stabilizing strength is attained by applying coatings of aluminum and some aluminum alloys, 0,5 to 2 microns thick, by pulling fibers through a melt. Analysis of the physicochemical interaction of fibers with the coatings is indicative of a selective dissolution of the fiber material atoms in the coating at stress concentrators with the result that the latter are smoothed out. In addition, the plasticizing effect is promoted by the relaxation of stresses in the coating at the stage of microplastic strain of the fiber. The second group includes coatings enhancing the wettability of fibers with metal melts. An essential role in improving the impregnation of carbon fiber strands and fabrics is played by the structure of coatings which exhibit a capillary effect, as the melt spreads, owing to the developed surface of a highly dispersed structure. The best results are obtained in double-layer coatings, the first, silicon carbide layer being protective and the second, molybdenum layer enhancing wettability.

Introduction

Applying plasticizing and wettability enhancing coatings on high-strength and high-modulus fibers is necessary because of the unstable mechanical properties of reinforcing fibers and the specific features of the process of producing composite materials, residing in that, on the one hand, fibers must be properly wetted and impregnated when, for example, liquid-phase techniques are employed and, on the other, one should avoid conversion of the fibers as a result of their physicochemical interaction with the matrix.

Effect of the Environment and Condition of the Surface on Plastic Strain and Failure of Materials (Analysis of the Literature)

Analysis of the data in the literature of the past decades is indicative of a highly specific role of surface layers in the macroscopic strain of materials (I-II). Many investigators point out that plastic deformation of material begins, as a rule, on its surface layers. They are discussing possible reasons of easy plastic flow at the initial stage of deformation.

On the other hand, there is ample evidence in the literature of the surface and surface layers performing the function of a barrier in the general process of microplastic strain of materials, including the numerous studies of the Rebinder effect (I2,I3), as well as the barrier nature of oxide films and various surface coatings (I-6). Thus, whether a surface layer is weak or strong depends, to a great extent, on the type of the environment and on the condition of the surface of the specimen under strain.

The effect of the environment and condition of the surface on the process of plastic strain of crystalline solids is discussed at length in Refs.(I-6).

One of the factors hindering free emergence of dislocations on the surface may be various solid surface layers in the crystal, i.e, either when the density of dislocations in the surface layers is high or the surface is covered by oxide, hydroxide, metallic, ceramic or other films. Studies into the possibility of a resistance to the movement of screw dislocations,

due to the presence of a thin film with an elastic modulus different from that of the base material, have shown that the higher the elastic modulus, the higher the resistance to the emergence of dislocations (14). Other characteristics of films, that can appreciably increase the resistance to the emergence of dislocations, are as follows: 1) differences in the lattice parameters of the film and substrate, 2) features of the crystal line structure and 3) the degree of polycrystallinity. Three types of barriers have been examined with dislocations interacting with thick and thin surface films (15); a) rows of dislocations, occurring on the substrate-film interface because of their lattices being different, b) a forest of dislocations immobilized by impurity atoms or by precipitates along the dislocation line, and c) the difference in the elastic moduli of the substrate and the surface film. If the shear modulus of the film exceeds that of the substrate, attractive forces of long-range order and repulsive forces of short-range order occur between the dislocations and surface film.

The effect of various metallic films precipitated on the surface of metallic single crystals on the critical shear stress has been studied by a number of investigators (2,3). A common conclusion can be drawn from these studies: metallic as well as oxide films increase the critical shear stress, but their effect on the general shape of stress-strain curves is much more significant. This effect manifests itself in that, in the case of coated single crystals, the strain curve almost is always higher than that corresponding to uncoated single crystals (2).

The effectiveness of surface films as dislocation barriers depends on the following factors: 1) adhesion between the film and substrate, 2) formation of alloys from the materials of the film and substrate, 3) structure and mechanical properties of the film, 4) difference in the elastic moduli of the film and substrate and 5) the degree of discrepancy between the lattices of the film and substrate.

Liquid and solid media may both increase and decrease the breaking stress and ultimate strain of crystals. Generally speaking, the media in which a crystal is easily soluble increase strength and plasticity, while those in which a crystal does not

dissolve well decrease them. The effects of the latter media include stress corrosion and brittleness in the presence of liquid metals. The mechanism of brittle failure under the effect of liquid metals is based on the decrease in the free energy of the solid metal along the melt interface, i.e. the decrease in the work of formation of new surface portions in the course of deformation and breakdown; on a microscale, this corresponds to easier rupture and rearrangement of interatomic bonds in the presence of definite adsorption-active atoms or molecules.

Normally, easily dissolving media are associated with the Joffe effect (16); according to Joffe, the significant increase in the strength (almost 25-fold) and plasticity (up to 45% strain) of KCl and NaCl crystals, observed in tests carried out in water, is due to complete elimination of surface cracks responsible for brittleness. Some investigators (17,18), modifying the original hypothesis advanced by Joffe, believe that the dissolving medium enhances the strength of a crystal owing to the reduced tendency of cracks to propagate. They hold that cracks need not be eliminated completely for the dissolution of a crystal is accompanied by separation of the solute at the apex of a crack, whereby the latter is "healed" owing to the longer radius of curvature of its apex.

Klassen-Heklyudova (19) has proposed to distinguish between two types of defects determining the properties of NaCl crystals: primary defects of the surface crack type and secondary defects occurring on the crystal surface under plastic strain. In this connection, the Joffe effect is subdivided into two (3,1,20): the Joffe effect proper, implying elimination of defects of the first type (surface cracks) in a liquid medium, and the Suzuki effect, eliminated whereby is the strengthened surface layer acting as a barrier to the emergence of a dislocation on the surface.

The dissolving media may effect breakdown characteristics also through elimination of easily activated surface sources of dislocation. This was shown by Stokes (20) on MgO crystals. A MgO crystal exposed, after chemical polishing, to a jet of air with SiC powder for "fresh" dislocation sources to be introduced featured a relatively low yield strength of $7 \cdot 10^5 \text{ N/m}^2$ with a greater number of sources being active.

stress concentrators, which boil down, mainly, to levelling off the geometric features (smoothing the microroughness) on the CF surface, namely, extending the radii of curvature of the crack apex, jogs, microseparations, etc., and to decreasing their height. In addition, the coating material must exhibit sufficient relaxation capacity in order to inhibit nucleation of cracks near surface stress concentrators and check the propagation of already existing microcracks.

From these considerations, we have selected nickel as the material for a plasticizing coating on carbon materials.

Experimental Data on the Effect of a Plasticizing Coating (Nickel) and Conditions of its Subsequent Heat Treatment on the Brittle Strength of Carbon Fibers

In the first series of experiments (21), applied on the polished surface of fine-grained graphite specimens, by electron bombardment evaporation in a vacuum of 10^{-5} mm Hg, where Ni films 0.9 to 1 μ m thick, the substrate being heated to 300°C. The sputtered specimens were then annealed in vacuum at 1,000°C for 10 hours to form a solid solution of C in Ni, whereby the right conditions were provided for the plasticizing effect to become manifest.

The effect was studied with the aid of a UPM-I microhardness indentation machine (22) which permits recording the kinetics of penetration of the indenter and determining, from the load penetration depth diagram, the depth of the restituted indentation, representative of the ability of the material to plastically deform. Fig. I represents, by way of an example, the results of such tests. It can be seen that with the Ni coating applied, the plasticizing effect manifests itself in a much greater depth of the restituted indentation, which exceeds that in the uncoated specimen (portion I) plus the thickness of the Ni film (portion II), i.e., the increment in the depth of the indentation, equal to portion III, is entirely due to the effect of plasticizing of the surface layers of fine-grained graphite.

In the second series of experiments, chemically applied on VMN-4 grade C fibers were Ni coatings 1 μ m thick. In this case, some batches of fibers were prepassivated by precipitating ato-

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Coatings to Improve the Brittle Strength of Carbon
Fibers

Thus, as can be inferred from the above-cited references, both solid as well as liquid and gaseous media may produce different effects, namely, strengthen and weaken the surface, as well as substantially affect the general process of macroscopic flow. Note, however, that all these specific effects manifest themselves to a maximum degree only when certain environment conditions are artificially introduced.

From analysis of the above experimental results, one can define the following basic causes of the effect of plasticizing of crystalline materials: a) in the case of microscopically plastic materials - easier emergence of dislocations and their pileups on the surface of a crystal and generation of subsurface dislocation sources as a result of a lower surface energy (Rebinder effect); b) in the case of brittle materials - healing or complete elimination of surface stress concentrators as a result of their selective dissolution in a liquid medium or a solid coating (Joffe effect).

Since carbon fibers (CF) are highly brittle, the first approach based on the Rebinder effect is not applicable to them for it reduces rather than raises the strength characteristics of the fiber. Therefore, in order to increase the brittle strength of CF, the second approach based on the Joffe effect should be used. It should be noted that, in this specific case, the traditional technique based on the Joffe effect, whereby a solid is immersed in a liquid medium, must be substituted by its solid-phase version, i.e. appropriate metallic coatings must be applied on CF in a solid phase with subsequent heat treatment to initiate diffusion processes of healing and dissolution of stress concentrators on the CF in the metallic coating. Hence, the basic requirements to a plasticizing coating must be as follows. The fiber material must readily dissolve in the coating without forming a brittle chemical compound with the latter. The coating application technique and performance characteristics (or subsequent heat treatment conditions) must provide for a sufficient diffusion mobility of the coating material on the CF surface to ensure the necessary conditions for healing the

Fig. I - Diagram of kinetic microhardness indentation by a diamond Vickers indenter into graphite without a Ni coating (a) and with a Ni coating (b).

mic pyrocarbon on their surface. Then, the fibers were annealed at 900°C for 100 hours or at $1,000^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 30, 60 or 100 hours to form a solid solution of C in Ni. After annealing, the strands of fibers were separated into individual filaments which were tested for stretching on a machine specially designed for the purpose, in an amount of 50 filaments for each state. The diameter of individual filaments varied from 4.6 to 9.8 mk. The results of these experiments are given in Fig.2 and 3. As can be seen from Fig.2, the deformation curve of a single filament is not strictly linear and features a great number of microdiscontinuities. This is indicative of the non-Hookian nature of the fiber deformation curve and suggestive of the possibility of microplastic shear along some planes in the process of the fiber's elongation (23).

The data represented in Fig.3 indicate that a Ni coating appreciably increases the strength of CF, particularly in combination with prepassivation of their surface. For example, if the initial strength of non-passivated and passivated CF 6 mm long is about 410 and 490 kg/mm^2 , respectively, after applying a Ni coating with subsequent annealing for 30 hours at $1,000^{\circ}\text{C}$,

Fig. 2 - Stress-strain diagram of a unitary filament of carbon fiber.

the strength increases up to 490 kg/mm^2 for non-passivated fibers and up to 640 kg/mm^2 for passivated ones. Extension of the annealing time up to 100 hours at $1,000^\circ\text{C}$ is marked by the strength of the non-passivated and passivated fibers further increasing to 650 and 810 kg/mm^2 , respectively.

Thus, the effect of improving the brittle strength of fibers increases with temperature and long annealing, which points to the decisive role played in this effect by the process of healing of the most dangerous microcracks and microseparations on the C fibers by Ni, as well as by the process of carbon's dissolution in Ni at highest microelevations and sporadic stress concentrators, which also results in a lower probability of occurrence of centers of brittle failure. Therewith, one should also take into account the sharp decrease in the scattering of strength values as the duration of annealing is extended. For example, the mean square dispersion of strength ($\Delta\sigma$) decreases from 60 and 88 kg/mm^2 for passivated and non-passivated CF, respectively, with the duration of annealing being equal to 30 hours at a temperature of $1,000^\circ\text{C}$, down to 28 and 14 kg/mm^2 when the annealing time is extended to 100 hours. Such a sharp decrease in $\Delta\sigma$ with longer annealing time for non-

Fig. 3 - Mean ultimate strength of passivated (1) and non-passivated (2) C fiber with a Ni coating versus annealing time at 1,000°C.

passivated fibers is probably due to the more intensive selective dissolution of C atoms at stress concentrators and at points of emergence of the end plane of the lattice on the fiber surface. Note that applying a Ni coating on CF without subsequent annealing, on the contrary, slightly reduces the fiber strength as opposed to its initial strength without the coating, because Ni precipitates rather non-uniformly on the surface of fibers (particularly passivated ones) and creates additional stress concentrators.

The higher strength of passivated fibers with a Ni coating, as compared to non-passivated fibers, can be explained by the fact that the process of passivation, residing in C being condensed from the vapor phase on the surface of CF, produces an additional effect of healing defects, which is further enhanced after annealing owing to the surface diffusion of the applied pyrocarbon and its precipitation at points of high stress concentrations on the CF surface. Besides, the applied pyrocarbon serves as an additional barrier to graphitization of CF in the presence of Ni (24) (transformation of the turbostratal structure of fibers to a three-dimensional crystalline structure of graphite, accompanied by a sharp decrease in strength), which

proceeds in a particularly active manner when the fiber surface is covered by a network of deep microflaws (cracks, microseparations etc.). It should be noted that, in the general case, since the process of graphitization of CF in contact with Ni starts only at a temperature of 800 to 850°C, coating CF with Ni is not dangerous for composite materials intended for an operating temperature range of up to 800°C. The process of passivation partially healing the most dangerous surface microdefects minimizes the probability of graphitization of CF. Therefore, the optimum temperature and duration of annealing of coated CF must be selected with due account for the kinetics of two opposing competitive processes: a) fiber strengthening with increasing temperature and duration of annealing, due to the intensification of the processes of surface diffusion of the plasticizing coating atoms and healing, thereby, the most dangerous microflaws on the CF surface, as well as due to the solid-phase dissolution of the most dangerous stress concentrators on the fiber surface in the Ni coating; and b) fiber weakening as a result of activated graphitization which is most active at local surface microflaws, hence, is a function of the history of obtaining and treating CF.

As can be seen from Fig.3, the annealing temperature being as high as 1,000°C permits the first process (fiber strengthening) to be significantly intensified, while the fiber weakening process is not yet fully manifest due to graphitization. However, as was shown by our experiments, the annealing temperature being further raised to 1,000°C, with annealing lasting from 30 to 100 hours, decreases rather than increases the strength of the coated fibers, most probably because of the predominant role of the weakening effect of fiber graphitization.

Metallization of Boron Fibers and its Effect on Strength Characteristics

One of the widely used techniques of obtaining metal coatings on fibers is by pulling the latter through melts of appropriate metals. The advantages of this process include simplicity and high capacity. Brief contact between the melt and the fiber eliminates or minimizes the possibility of formation of brittle phase layers on the coating-fiber interface, which might

eventually worsen the mechanical properties of the composition.

Fibers were metallized in an apparatus including a resistance furnace in which the melt was heated to a temperature of $1,100^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a fiber pulling mechanism with the pulling speed being adjustable from 3.6 to 100 mm/sec. In the course of the experiments, the melt temperature, fiber pulling speed, height of the melt column, and the die orifice diameter were changed. The quality of the coating was controlled visually as well as with the aid of a "Neophot-2" optical microscope and an ISM-U3 scanning electron microscope. To determine the optimum pulling conditions, coated wire specimens were tested for stretching on an Instron TDM, SN machine. At least 60 specimens were tested for each process to determine the mean square value of strength and the variation coefficient. Monofilaments of silicon carbide, B, as well as B coated with silicon carbide and boron carbide were pulled through melts of ALI aluminum and its alloys with silicon (up to 12% by weight), magnesium (up to 5.8% by weight), manganese (up to 0.9% by weight), and Ni (6.18% by weight).

Pulling of B and B_4C coated boron filaments through the melt always produced a dense continuous coating. The coating thickness increased with the die orifice diameter and with decreasing melt temperature and pulling speed (Fig.4). If the melt was not sufficiently heated or if the melt column was not sufficiently high, the coating became porous. As a rule, the melt column height exceeded 40 mm. The die being contaminated with oxides resulted in a mechanical damage to the coating, therefore, most of the experiments were conducted using dies with orifice diameters equal to or greater than 0.5 mm to prevent the coating from being damaged. Coatings of aluminum alloys with magnesium, Cu and Si featured a cellular-dendritic structure, which was an indication of the coating material being crystallized after the die.

We failed to coat SiC-coated boron filaments (borsic) with Al and its alloy with 6.18% of Ni in the test melt temperature range (700 to 900°C) and at pulling speeds of 7 to 70 mm/sec. Silumin AI2 (12% by weight of Si) formed a coating on borsic at pulling speeds of 9 and 16 mm/sec and melt temperatures of 650 and 750°C , respectively. In this case, partial peeling of the

Fig. 4 - Thickness of coating on boron fibers (a) and silicon carbide fibers (b) versus melt temperature (I), fiber pulling speed (2) and die orifice diameter (3).

coating was observed. When borsic was pulled through melts of aluminum-magnesium alloy AMg5 (Al - 0.5% Mg - 0.5% Mn) and duralumin DI6 (Al - 4% Cu - 1.8% Mg - 0.9% Mn), the resulting coating was continuous and strong.

Attempts to coat silicon carbide and borsic filaments with pure aluminum and Al-Ni alloy failed. Satisfactory coatings on silicon carbide were obtained from silumin AL2 at a pulling speed of no more than 5.5 mm/sec and a melt temperature of 750°C , and from duralumin DI6 at pulling speeds of at least 8 mm/sec and a melt temperature of at least 300°C .

The specific features of Al alloy coatings on high-modulus fibers, revealed during the experiments, are due to the differences in their wettability. According to Ref. (25), the ability of crystals with a predominantly covalent atomic bond, such as boron and silicon carbide, to be wetted by the same metal melts increases with the decreasing fraction of the ionic component of the bond. The examined fibrous materials form the following series in order of decreasing fraction of the ionic component of the bond: silicon carbide \rightarrow boron carbide \rightarrow boron. This is why boron and boron coated with boron carbide exhibited, in

tests where filaments were pulled through an Al melt, a better wettability than borsic and silicon carbide. We succeeded in metallizing borsic and silicon carbide fibers by alloying the melt with silicon and magnesium. According to Ref.(26), these elements reduce the surface tension of an Al melt. The surface activity is particularly pronounced in the case of magnesium: adding 1 at.% of magnesium to the Al melt reduces the surface tension from 860 to 690 dynes per cm. Ni, Cu, Mn and Al are inactive when added, i.e., they do not tangibly affect the surface tension of the melt, nor they improve the wettability of borsic and silicon carbide fibers.

Summarized in Table I are the results of tensile tests of coated specimens and fibers exposed to the melt but not coated or having their coatings chemically removed. As can be seen from the table, the instability of the properties of starting fibers leads to the instability of the results of testing semiproducts. For example, uncoated borsic filaments pulled through the melt are stronger or weaker than the starting fiber (pp. I4, I8, I9). As a rule, boron filaments become weaker after having been pulled through the melt, and the lower the pulling speed and the higher the melt temperature, the weaker the filaments become (pp.II-I3). The lowest strength of the extracted filaments seems to be due to their being damaged during chemical cleansing, since coated filaments are invariably stronger (pp.2-4). Therefore, it was decided that testing filaments extracted from semiproducts by pickling is not worthwhile. Comparison of the results of testing coated specimens is more significant.

The best strength characteristics were obtained when B filaments coated with silumin, DI6 and AMg5 alloy were tested at the lowest melt temperatures (pp.6-10). The B filaments turned out to be less sensitive to the thermal conditions of the process (pp.I4,I5,I8,I9). The strength of filaments with a silumin and duralumin coating up to 1 mk thick is, in general, greater than that of the starting fibers.

Coating silicon carbide filaments with Al and its alloys resulted in a loss of strength (pp.21-23). In the case of an uncoated filament pulled through the melt, the strength was reduced by 6% (pp.20 and 24). The best results were obtained when

Table I. Regime of Pulling and Mechanical
Properties of Fibers with Deposits
on Them

N	Fiber	Matrix	Matrix temperature T°C	Rate of pulling $\frac{\text{mm}}{\text{sec}}$	Melted matrix height mm	Die diameter, mm	Deposit thickness, mm	kg/mm ²	Variation coefficient %
I	B*	-	-	-	-	-	-	252,7	24
2	B	ADI	820	70	50	0,5	0,0005	201,3	19
3		-"-	770	30	40	0,5	0,0085	196,3	19
4		-"-	770	70	40	0,5	0,003	212,9	21
5		Al- -6,18Ni	750	14	35	0,35	0,0025	206,8	18
6		AL2	700	4	50	0,5	0,001	262,6	12
7		-"-	750	4	50	0,5	0,002	248,2	11
8		-"-	800	4	50	0,5	0,003	208,7	19
9	B	AMg5	700	16	40	0,5	0,004	265,7	12
10		-"-	750	16	40	0,5	0,006	231,5	14
11	B**	ADI	770	30	50	0,5	-	140	15
12		-"-	770	70	50	0,5	-	194	17
13.		-"-	820	70	50	0,5	-	135	12,5
14	B+S1C*	-	-	-	-	-	-	183,7	19
15	B+S1C	DI6	740	10,8	40	0,5	0,0005	195,1	6
16		AL2	650	30	40	0,5	0,0005	195,9	14
17		AMg5	800	30	40	0,5	0,003	173,5	16
18	B+S1C***	ADI	800	30	50	0,5	-	142,8	15
19		Al+6,18% Ni	900	8,4	40	0,5	-	198	12
20	S1C*	-	-	-	-	-	0,0015	197,8	21,5
21	S1C	DI6	750	8,0	45	0,8	0,005	142,4	21,3
22		-"-	800	5,5	45	0,8	0,0015	189,5	16,8
23		AMg5	800	8,6	45	0,8	0,0025	161,2	15,9
24	S1C***	AL2	750	8,0	45	0,8	-	185,5	21,5
25	B+B ₄ C*	-	-	-	-	-	-	329,6	14
26	B+B ₄ C	AMg5	700	8,0	40	0,5	0,003	335,2	12
27		AL2	700	16,0	40	0,5	0,003	356	14
28		-"-	850	16,0	40	0,5	0,0025	347,5	10

*) initial fibre; **) coating is removed by etching; ***) fibre without deposit

silicon carbide filaments were pulled through a silumin melt at a temperature of 750°C , the time of contact with the melt being about 8 seconds. B_4C -coated boron filaments practically did not weaken as they were pulled through the melt (pp.25-28). An important result of mechanical tests was the stable decrease in the variation coefficients, revealed during the experiments. Stability of properties was exhibited by high-modulus fibers of all types with all kinds of coatings. B and borsic specimens with a 2 mk thick coating were marked by a two and even three-fold decrease in the variation coefficient. This fact gains in importance when the technique of pulling fibers through a melt is combined with other processes of producing composite materials.

Wetting and Impregnation of Carbon Fibers with Wettability Enhancing Coatings

One of the prerequisites of obtaining composite materials featuring improved physicommechanical properties and based on an Al matrix reinforced with C fibers is high quality of impregnation of the fiber strands with the melt of the matrix, which may be difficult because of the poor wettability of the carbon fiber surface with respect to aluminum and its alloys. Currently produced high-strength and high-modulus carbon fibers are essentially straight or twisted multifilament strands from which fabrics and tapes are produced. Depending on the application, the number of filaments in a strand may vary from several hundred to several thousand, the diameter of each filament varying from 1 to 2 mk. Impregnation of such strands or fabrics from C fibers with melts of metals, particularly Al alloys, in vacuum or under positive pressure is, at present, one of the promising ways to produce composite materials.

A.P.Varenkov and V.I.Kostikov (27), who studied the wettability of VMN-4 carbon fibers in Al-base melts at a negative pressure of $2,10^{-4}$ mm Hg by the sessile drop method have shown that wetting angles θ are greater than 90° . The introduction of Ti and Ni additives (up to 1.0% by weight) into the Al melt affects but insignificantly angle θ . The use of silicon carbide, Cu and Ni as chemically applied coatings on C fibers, up to tenths of a micron thick, does not improve the wettability. In

the case of a silicon carbide coating, the inadequate impregnation of C fibers is due to the poor wettability in the silicon-carbide-Al melts system, while in the case of Cu and Ni coatings, it is due to the latter dissolving in the melt because of the long contact (equilibrium values of θ under the experimental conditions (27) were achieved over periods of time as long as several minutes). In other words, the data on the wettability and flow of Al melts in the latter case cannot be regarded as results obtained in a metal-metal system. Therefore, in order to improve the wettability of C fibers in Al melts by applying metal coatings (particularly Ni coatings) such conditions are required as would ensure a high speed of flow and considerably (by one order of magnitude) shorten the time of contact of the coating with the melt. According to the same authors, the melt will penetrate into strands of fibers only under a positive pressure not exceeding 1 atm, which follows from calculations of the ratio of the capillary and positive pressure to the wetting angle and the volume fraction of the C fibers in the liquid Al matrix at 925 and 1,083°C. Experimental verification of this assumption in Ref.(27) has shown that under a small positive (external) pressure, the rate of impregnation of fibers with an Al melt with an addition of 1.0% by weight of Ti was 50 cm/sec.

Attempts to enhance wettability by increasing the thickness of a Ni coating under conditions of long contact between the fibers and melts (θ decreases from 120 to 40-50° within 5 to 10 minutes) lead to other complications associated with Al being saturated with Ni at intolerably high concentrations and, as a consequence, embrittlement of the matrix and fibers because Al_3Ni intermetallide phase inclusions are formed (28).

In view of the above, the techniques of impregnating carbon fibers and fabrics with melts based on Al were improved over the past 2-3 years by applying an external positive pressure. However, even under these conditions, the highest tensile strength of an Al-C fiber composite material with the volume fraction of the fibers being 40 to 60% did not exceed 70-80 kg/mm², whereas, according to the additivity rule, much higher values would be expected (100 to 120 kg/mm²). This is primarily due to the following two factors: 1) a decrease in the initial-

ly high strength of the fibers on contact with the melt at elevated temperatures (900 to 1,100°C) because of the fibers' graphitization and formation of carbides; and 2) insufficiently even distribution of fibers in the matrix, characterized by defects in the form of isolated groups of filaments not separated by the matrix and, therefore, serving as natural internal stress concentrators. The second cause results in that, as the volume fraction of C fibers exceeds 30-35%, the strength of the composite material not only remains the same but starts to decrease due to the increasing number of filament groups not impregnated with the melt.

To obviate these disadvantages, it was necessary to find a combination of such barrier ceramic and metal coatings that, in contrast with a Ni coating, would protect fibers, as well as ensure effective wetting and impregnation of C fiber strands with Al melts at lower temperatures. Earlier, coatings of refractory metals (Mo, W) had been developed by the authors, applied on carbon fibers and fabrics by the carbonyl method (29). Depending on the substrate heating temperature, the nature of the substrate and the rate of feeding carbonyl, the authors succeeded in obtaining porous molybdenum and W coatings with a developed disperse surface providing for the right conditions for the capillary effect of wetting with melts (Fig.5, a,b,c), which ensured sufficiently good impregnation of C fiber strands with Al, even distribution of fibers across the specimen, and adequate adhesion of the coating to the fibers (30). Determining the relationship between the minimum degree of evacuation and the quality of impregnation with different types of coatings on carbon fiber was of practical as well as theoretical interest. As metal melts use was made, in studying the wetting characteristics, of eutectic alloys of Al with Ni (5.7% by weight) and Si (11% by weight). C fibers were impregnated with Al melts on a TVV-5 unit. The impregnation parameters were as follows: melt temperature - 800°C, positive argon pressure - 0,4 atm. The starting material was C fibers precoated with silicon carbide performing the function of a barrier coat. The Ni coating was applied chemically with the fibers being heated up to 750°C and the carbonyl decomposition temperature equalling 50°C. The structure of the Mo coating is shown in Fig.5 c. Metallographic analysis of

Fig. 5 - Coatings of refractory metals on carbon fibers: a) porous tungsten coating, precipitation temperature 600°C ; x 6000; b) dense tungsten coating, precipitation temperature 700°C ; x 5000; c) molybdenum coating with developed disperse surface, precipitation temperature 750°C , x 4500.

the obtained coatings reveals the relationship between the quality of impregnation and the type of coating as well as the degree of evacuation (Table II). The starting fibers coated with SiC do not permit impregnation with Al-Ni and Al-Si eutectic alloys even at a vacuum of 10^{-5} mm Hg. The Ni coating slightly improves the wettability of the starting fibers at this vacuum. C fibers are partially impregnated with the metal melt.

A different picture is observed when Mo-coated C fibers are impregnated. The even distribution of C filaments in the metal matrix (Fig.6 a,b) is ensured by the fact that each filament in the strand is impregnated with metal, while the developed disperse surface permits penetration of the Al matrix into the coating structure owing to the capillary effect. Note that adequate impregnation of carbon fibers coated with Mo takes place at a vacuum of 10^{-3} mm Hg.

However, as the vacuum is brought to 10^{-2} mm Hg, the impregnation is but partial (Fig.6b). Such a vacuum is not sufficient for proper impregnation of carbon fibers even when capilla-

Fig. 6 - Microstructure of a composite material based on an Al-5.7 Ni matrix with carbon fibers coated with Mo in a vacuum of: a) 10^{-5} mm Hg; x 700; b) 10^{-3} mm Hg, x 700; c) 10^{-2} mm Hg, x 700.

ry forces come into play.

In the case of Al-Si eutectic, similar results have been obtained. Fibers impregnated with silicon carbide as well as silicon carbide and Ni were not impregnated even at a vacuum of 10^{-5} mm Hg (Table II).

Table II.

Matrix wt %	Coating on carbon fiber	Vacuum		
		10^{-2} mm Hg	10^{-3} mm Hg	10^{-5} mm Hg
Al-5.7Ni	SiC	no impregnat.	no impregnat.	no impregnat.
	SiC + Ni	no impregnat.	no impregnat.	partial impreg.
	SiC + Mo	partial impreg.	good impreg.	good impreg.
Al-IISi	SiC	no impregnat.	no impregnat.	no impregnat.
	SiC + Ni	no impregnat.	no impregnat.	no impregnat.
	SiC + Mo	partial impreg.	good impreg.	good impreg.

Conclusion

It has been shown that coating of passivated and non-pas-

sivated carbon fibers with Ni with subsequent annealing at 1,000°C for 100 hours substantially improves their tensile strength and minimizes the mean square dispersion of strength values.

Application of Al coatings 0.5 to 2 mm thick on B and silicon carbide fibers by pulling through the melt stabilizes the strength characteristics of fibers.

The best results of wetting C fibers and impregnating them with Al melts at a lower temperature and vacuum were obtained when the coating was a combination of two layers: the first, protective layer of silicon carbide and the second, wettability enhancing layer of such transition metals as Mo which is adequately wetted with Al and features lesser affinity to C than silicon. An important role in increasing the effectiveness of coating strands and fabrics of carbon fibers is played by the structure of the Mo coating having a highly developed and disperse surface, whereby the melt is spread over the coating surface owing to the capillary effect.

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